

IOSIPESCU TEST TO CHARACTERIZE MODE II DELAMINATION RESISTANCE OF FIBRE-REINFORCED POLYMERS

P.-Y. B. Jar*, S. McKinney

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Alberta, Edmonton, AB, Canada,

* Corresponding author (ben.jar@ualberta.ca)

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1 Introduction

Delamination has long been a serious problem for fibre-reinforced polymers (FRP). Its occurrence not only reduces FRP's load-bearing capacity, but also damages the structural integrity to cause catastrophic failure without much warning in advance. Delamination is known to occur in tensile (mode I), in-plane shear (mode II) and out-of-plane tear (mode III) loading. Although some standards are available for characterizing the delamination resistance, such as ASTM D5528 for mode I, and JSA K7086 for mode II [1], there still exist some interests in developing special tests to characterize delamination resistance of FRP products of which dimensions cannot meet the requirements specified in the standards.

Objective of our research in this area is in two aspects. One, like most of the work in the literature, is to characterize FRP's resistance to delamination, and the other is to examine fundamental issues on fracture behaviour by treating delamination as a special fracture scenario, i.e., with a well-defined crack growth path. For the latter objective, our research is to explore feasibility of simulating the delamination growth using finite element (FE) method.

This paper presents a study that uses Iosipescu loading [2] on double-edge-notched (DEN) specimens. Iosipescu test is commonly used to determine material or adhesive strength when subjected to shear loading. Typical specimen for Iosipescu test is a short beam with two V-notches of 90° angle. For determining adhesive strength, the beam consists of two equal halves, made of substrate material for the adhesive, and the adhesive is used to glue the two halves together [3].

Iosipescu test has also been used to characterize FRP's strength. However, most FRP specimens used for the Iosipescu test have fibre running across the ligament length. As a result, pure shear fracture is not generated and the results are only useful for the purpose of material comparison. Specimens used in the current study have fibre running parallel to the ligament length. With the notches introduced in the central interlaminar region, the test is used to quantify delamination resistance of FRP in a pure shear loading mode.

The paper presents results from an experimental study that uses regression analysis to determine essential part of energy consumption for delamination development in FRP. The regression analysis is based on a concept commonly known as essential work of fracture (EWF) that determines fracture toughness when ductile deformation is developed before the crack growth. The paper will show that even with largely elastic deformation and brittle fracture, the EWF concept is still applicable to characterization of FRP's mode II delamination resistance.

In addition to the experimental testing, FE simulation is used to reveal mechanisms involved in the delamination development in FRP during the Iosipescu test. The paper provides updates of the FE simulation work, which is expected to complete before the conference, thus will be presented in detail in the conference.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials Characterization

Each specimen for the Iosipescu test consists of an FRP piece in the centre, sandwiched by a rectangular aluminum tab on each side. All FRP pieces of the

same ligament length were cut from the same unidirectional glass/epoxy panel of nominally 4.7 mm thick, manufactured using a hand layup technique. Sixteen layers of E-glass fibre sheets of two different fibre weights were used to make the FRP panel, 9 oz/yd² (305.2 g/m²) for the middle six layers and 4.5 oz/yd² (152.6 g/m²) for the outer ten layers. Epoxy resin for the matrix is a two-part system provided by Momentive, consisting of Epon 826 and Epikure 9551 that are a bisphenol-A matrix and a polyamine hardener, respectively, at a mixing ratio of 100:36 by weight. Curing procedure of the FRP followed that reported by Hu et al. [4], i.e. at 50°C for 2 hours and then, 120°C for 2.5 hours. A vacuum chamber is used during the layup process to control the void content.

FRP pieces used for the Iosipescu test do not contain any stitching threads in the middle six layers, in order to avoid influence of the stitching threads on the delamination initiation and growth. Aluminum foil of 20 µm thick was used to introduce the edge notches. The foil was cut with a new razor blade and the foil edges flattened to ensure sharpness of the notch tip.

Rough cuts of the FRP pieces were made first with diamond-tipped abrasive saws, and then the finishing cuts using a low speed (60 rpm) saw. The notches were gently opened using a razor blade. Note that the finishing cuts were made after the notches were opened, to prevent the possibility of damaging the specimen. Final dimensions of the FRP pieces, 20x14 mm², were reached by dry sanding. Symmetry of the FRP pieces was controlled to ensure equal length of the two notches.

Two methods were used to determine fiber volume fraction (V_f) of the FRP pieces. The first is modified from ASTM standard D3171, due to the use of fibre sheets of different weight, and the second optical microscopy. The former is based on the following equation,

$$V_f = \frac{A_a N_a + A_b N_b}{10 \rho_f (h_a + h_b)} \quad (1)$$

where V_f is fiber volume fraction, A area density of glass fibre (g/m²), N number of fiber layers, ρ_f fibre density (g/cm³), and h thickness (cm) of panel

occupied by the given fiber type, with subscript a and b standing for the fibre type.

Fiber volume fraction determined from the microscopy was based on samples cut through the ligament area, in the direction normal to the fiber. Individual fibers were identified using Adobe Photoshop, and fraction of surface area covered by fiber using NIH Image J.

Void content in the FRP pieces was determined according to ASTM D792, based on the difference of theoretical density and the measured density from the FRP pieces. Equation (2) was used to determine the measured density (D):

$$D = \frac{a}{a + w - b} \rho_w \quad (2)$$

where a is weight of the FRP piece in air (mass dependent), b its weight when suspended in water by a wire (volume dependent), w weight of the wire, and ρ_w water density.

The theoretical density (T) of FRP is calculated based on the theoretical density of fibre and matrix, ρ_f and ρ_m , respectively, using the following equation:

$$T = V_f \rho_f + (1 - V_f) \rho_m \quad (3)$$

Difference between D and T is attributed to the presence of voids. Thus, equation (4) is used to determine the void content in percentage (V_v).

$$V_v = 100 \times \frac{T - D}{T} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Iosipescu Test

Figure 1 depicts the setup of Iosipescu test used in this study. Fibre in the central FRP piece is oriented in the vertical direction. As marked by two short black lines, the notches are from the top and bottom edges of the FRP piece, both introduced in the central interlaminar region. The Iosipescu test generates delamination by shearing off the FRP piece into two halves through the ligament region between the notches.

Tests were conducted with a Galdabini Quasar 100 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 1

mm/min. At least three tests were conducted for each ligament length that ranges from 2 to 6 mm.

Load-displacement curves are recorded from the tests, and the corresponding energy consumption calculated for the regression analysis, to determine the resistance to the delamination development.

Figure 1 Iosipescu test set-up

2.3 Auxiliary Delamination Tests

In addition to Iosipescu test, end-notched flexure (ENF) tests were conducted to evaluate mode II delamination resistance of the same FRP. In view of the relatively thin FRP panel with a medium level of fibre volume fraction, a span length of 60 mm was chosen to prevent from the large deflection required to generate the interlaminar fracture. As recommended in ref. [5], the initial crack length is quarter of span length, i.e. 15 mm. Six ENF specimens were tested at the crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

Critical energy release rate (G_{IIc}) from the ENF test is calculated based on the following equation [6].

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9a^2 P \delta}{2B(2L_s^2 + 3a^3)} \quad (5)$$

where a is crack length, P force, δ the corresponding deflection, B beam width, and L_s half span length (30 mm).

Three different points were selected to measure G_{IIc} , the nonlinear point, the 5% offset point, and the maximum load point. The nonlinear point was determined by first establishing a least squares regression line to fit to the linear section of the load-

displacement curve. Then, the nonlinear point was chosen to be the point at which the force was 1% lower than the regression line. The 5% offset point is the intersection of the original force curve with a line corresponding to a 5% increase of the initial compliance.

3 EWF Method

Iosipescu test results are analyzed based on the EWF concept, originally developed for determining ductile fracture toughness in the plane-stress condition. The EWF concept was first applied to thin metals in tension [7], and later to polymers [8].

The underlying principle for the EWF method is the presence of two distinct mechanisms during the fracture development. One is essential to form the fracture surface, for which the amount of energy consumed depends on the size of the ligament cross sectional area. The other is non-essential for the fracture, and is usually the plastic deformation in the ligament region. Size of the plastic deformation zone is needed to determine the energy consumed for its development.

Based on the above two mechanisms, total energy required for fracture can be expressed in terms of the essential and the non-essential parts of energy for the crack development:

$$W_f = w_e \cdot L \cdot t + w_p \cdot \beta L \cdot L \cdot t \quad (6)$$

where w_e is EWF per unit fracture area, w_p the geometry-dependent non-essential energy per unit volume, L ligament length, t specimen thickness and β shape factor for the deformation zone.

In this study, values for W_f from Iosipescu specimens are calculated from the force-stroke curve, and plotted as a function of L after normalization with ligament area ($L \cdot t$), named specific work of fracture (SWF). It has been shown for many metals and polymers [8-9] that such a plot shows a linear trend. Thus by extrapolating to $L=0$, the geometry-dependent non-essential energy is removed, and w_e value that represents the delamination fracture toughness is determined.

The EWF concept has been applied to Iosipescu test of high density polyethylene (HDPE) and

poly(acrylonitrile butadiene styrene) (ABS), for determining their mode II fracture toughness [10-11]. The results suggest that the concept is indeed applicable if mode II fracture behaviour can be generated, which for ABS and HDPE is by introducing V-shaped grooves along the ligament length between the notch tips.

Since FRP specimen used in the current study has orthotropic properties, with stiffness along the fibre direction being much higher than that in the other two directions, side grooves are not needed to induce the mode II fracture.

4 Finite Element Simulations

An FE model is used to mimic Iosipescu testing using ABAQUS 6.9, to investigate mechanisms involved in the experiments.

4.1 The Model

FE model used to simulate the Iosipescu testing is presented in Figure 2. Figure 2(a) shows the overall geometry and the mesh pattern, and 2(b) the model of the FRP piece (top) and the central interlaminar region (bottom). All dimensions of the model follow those used in the experiment. Boundary conditions are enforced along the outer edges of the moving and fixed Iosipescu jaws.

Elastic properties for each component of the specimen are summarized in Table 1. For the two outer layers in the FRP piece, the elastic properties are assumed to be uniform, based on fibre volume fraction (V_f) of 25.4%. For the middle 6 layers, elastic properties for fibre bundles are based on V_f of 45%. As shown in Figure 2, the model considers individual fibre bundles for the middle 6 layers, separated by resin-rich regions. A layer of cohesive zone is introduced in the central interlaminar region where crack is developed during the simulation.

Due to limitation in the modeling capacity, Figure 2 only represents a 2-dimensional view of the Iosipescu test, on plane 1-3 that is parallel to the front view of the test, i.e. Figure 1. Since fibre distribution along direction 2 is not uniform, as shown by the cross-sectional view on plane 2-3 in Figure 3, two sectional views (sections A and B in Figure 3) need to be considered for the FE modeling,

in order to represent variation of the fibre bundle distribution in direction 2. The 2-D model in Figure 2 represents section A in Figure 3. Section B in Figure 3 can also be simulated using the model in Figure 2, by changing properties for the two fibre bundles that are closest to the central interlaminar region to the properties of resin-rich region. However, a preliminary study suggests that models for the two cross sections generate little difference in the force-stroke curve. Therefore, FE results presented here are based on the model for section A of Figure 3, that is, with 6 fibre bundles in the central region.

Note that fibre bundles in Figure 3 are idealized as rounded rectangles arranged in a regular pattern, to have the same fraction of fibre bundle area as that in the central six layers of the FRP piece. Within each fibre bundle, the elastic properties, as given in Table 1, are considered to be homogeneous and orthotropic.

4.2 Hill Plasticity

Plastic deformation of central fibre bundles is based on the Hill plasticity model [12] that requires a criterion for yield initiation and an evolution law for the deformation. In this study, the equivalent stress for the Hill's yield criterion is an adaptation of the von Mises criterion with a relative weight function assigned to each stress component. Equation (7) gives the Hill stress function. The Hill potential is determined using yield ratios R_{ij} in equation (8), defined as the ratio of the yield stress under a unidirectional stress state to a reference yield stress which is selected to be the yield stress of epoxy [13].

$$f(\sigma) = \sqrt{F(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + G(\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + H(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 2L\sigma_{23}^2 + 2M\sigma_{31}^2 + 2N\sigma_{12}^2} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{22}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{33}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{11}^2} \right), & L &= \frac{3}{2R_{23}^2}, \\ G &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{33}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{11}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{22}^2} \right), & M &= \frac{3}{2R_{13}^2}, \\ H &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{R_{11}^2} + \frac{1}{R_{22}^2} - \frac{1}{R_{33}^2} \right), & N &= \frac{3}{2R_{12}^2}, \end{aligned} \quad R_{ij} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}}{\sigma^0} \quad (8)$$

The above Hill potential was set so that the FE model only responds to transverse normal stress in direction 3 and shear stress 13. The yield ratios and

their corresponding coefficients for the Hill potential are listed in Table 2.

Table 1 Elastic properties used for the FE model

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)
Outer Layer	24.1	6.2	4.5	0.275	0.275	0.3	1.8	1.8	1.3
Fiber Bundle	38.6	8.27	8.27	0.26	0.26	0.321	4.14	4.14	3.13
Resin Rich	3.87	-	-	-	0.42	-	-	-	-
Aluminum Tab	70	-	-	-	0.33	-	-	-	-
Steel Jaw	200	-	-	-	0.30	-	-	-	-

Figure 2 FE model for Iosipescu test: (a) the overall model, and (b) the model for the FRP piece

In this study, response of the fibre bundles under transverse tension and shear is regarded to be the same as that of the interlaminar resin-rich region, but remains elastic throughout the simulation.

Properties for the resin-rich regions are assumed to be isotropic, for which the elastic-plastic properties are based on the published data [4] for the pure resin with the stiffness scaled up roughly about 30%, to support the empirical stress for the onset of fracture. Figure 4 shows the elastic-plastic response of the neat resin used in the study and that for the corresponding resin-rich region.

4.3 Cohesive Element

The fracture development is simulated using a cohesive zone which is one element thick and transfers stress from one side to the other as a surface traction. Damage is modeled using stiffness degradation to allow the progressive failure, and is initiated when a stress component (in this case shear stress) reaches its maximum value. Further separation results in damage propagation which is governed by equation (9) and the corresponding stiffness by equation (10). Value for the damage coefficient D is between 0 (undamaged) and 1 (completely damaged). The corresponding softening behavior is demonstrated in Figure 5, with the maximum shear stress set at 54 MPa and G_{IIc} 2.18 kJ/m² according to the Iosipescu test result, as to be presented in the results section.

$$D = \frac{\delta_f (\delta_{max} - \delta_o)}{\delta_{max} (\delta_f - \delta_o)} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{with } \delta_f = \frac{2G}{\tau_{int}} \text{ and } \delta_o = \frac{\tau_{int}}{K_o}$$

$$K = (1 - D)K_o \quad (10)$$

where K is degraded stiffness, K_o undamaged stiffness, δ_{max} maximum displacement in the loading history, δ_f fracture displacement, δ_o displacement at the damage initiation, and τ_{int} stress for the damage initiation.

Initial stiffness of the cohesive zone was determined using equation (11), by adapting a technique proposed by Turon et al. [14], originally for mode I delamination in a double cantilever beam specimen.

$$K_{ss} = \frac{\alpha G_{13}}{t} \quad (11)$$

where K_{ss} is stiffness in tangential direction, G_{13} out-of-plane shear modulus, t thickness of interlaminar resin-rich region, and α scaling parameter. Value for α in the current study is chosen to be 50.

Table 2 Yield ratios and coefficients for Hill Potential

Yield Ratio	R_1	R_2	R_3	R_{12}	R_{13}	R_{23}
		100	1	1	1	1
Hill Potential	F	G	H	L	M	N
	0.99995	5×10^{-5}	5×10^{-5}	1.5×10^{-4}	1.5	1.5

Figure 3 Idealized shape and distribution of fibre bundles on cross section 2-3 in the middle six layers

The glue that bonds the FRP piece to the tabs is also modeled with cohesive elements in order to take advantage of their surface traction formulation. Shear traction stiffness of the adhesive surface is set at 150 MPa/mm. However, damage is not considered for the adhesive bonding. In addition, the glue is assumed to be rigid under normal loading, by setting its normal stiffness at 10^7 MPa/mm.

Contact is defined between aluminum tabs and steel jaws to provide realistic clamping, with the coefficient of static friction set at 0.47 [15].

Figure 4 Stress-strain curve of pure resin (dashed line) and resin-rich region (solid line) used in this study

Figure 5 Softening behaviour of cohesive elements

Because of unstable crack growth in the Iosipescu test, Riks arc length method [16], adopted by Crisfield for FE simulation [17], is used in the final loading step of the simulation.

5 Results and Analysis

5.1 Material Characterization

Typical microstructure on a cross section of an FRP piece is shown in Figure 6, taken from the ligament area of an unbroken sample on a cross section perpendicular to the fibre bundles. The ellipse-like zones of darker color are fibre bundles which are closer together in the middle region and farther apart outside. Dark spots in each fibre bundle are cross section of individual fibres. Results of fibre volume fraction (V_f) for the middle and outer regions and the overall void content are summarized in Table 3. As shown in the table, average V_f for the middle 6 fibre layers is 38.5%. Although V_f for the outer layers is

much lower, 21%, the outer layers do not have any significant role on the delamination development. Note that fibre bundles in the middle 6 layers have spread out more evenly than that in the outer layers,

because stitching threads in the former were removed. Large dark spots in Figure 6 are voids, which on average is about 2.5% in volume, as shown in Table 3.

Figure 6 Microstructure of the FRP piece

Table 3 Properties of inspected FRP pieces

Source	Density (kg/m ³)	Outer V _f (%)	Middle V _f (%)	Void (%)	
Microscopy	-	25.4%	38.6%	-	
Density	#1	1578	20.7%	37.9%	2.8%
	#2	1593	20.9%	38.3%	1.5%
	#3	1580	21.5%	39.4%	3.1%
Averages	1584	21.0%	38.5%	2.5%	

5.2 Mechanical Tests (Iosipescu and ENF)

A typical curve of force versus stroke from the Iosipescu test is shown in Figure 7. The curve consists of four sections: 1) a short takeoff in which the fixture is settling, 2) a linear region under stable loading, 3) a short softening region, and 4) a sudden, unstable crack growth. W_f is calculated from the area covered by the curve up to the peak load, after removing the takeoff section and extrapolating the linear region back to zero force. Peak force is selected for W_f calculation because it is likely to be the point for on-set of delamination and is easily identified, thus assuring reliability of the results.

Figure 8 summarizes all specific work of fracture (SWF) from the Iosipescu tests and G_{IIc} from ENF tests (at $L=0$ mm, with solid circles from non-linear point and cross from maximum load). The figure suggests that SWF increases with the increase of ligament length L up to 5 mm, but then remains relatively constant for further increase of L to 6 mm. Extrapolating SWF back to $L=0$ coincides with G_{IIc}

value from the non-linear point, with the average value of 2.18 kJ/m² for w_e . Averaged of the G_{IIc} values from the ENF tests are given in Table 4.

Figure 7 A typical curve from the Iosipescu test

Deviation from the linear trend in Figure 8, for data of $L=6$ mm, is believed to be the result of change in mechanisms involved for the delamination development. Specifically, it is believed that fiber buckling is involved for crack growth in specimens with $L=6$ mm. Evidence for the fibre buckling is shown in Figure 9 which compares fracture surfaces from two post-test specimens, the left with $L=5$ mm and the right $L=6$ mm. The left photograph (for $L=5$ mm) shows a sharp boundary between the pre-notch and the fracture surface, which is a typical behaviour for specimens of all ligament lengths except $L=6$ mm. The right photograph (for $L=6$ mm), on the other hand, shows several splitting

fiber bundles that cross the boundary between the fractured ligament area and the pre-notch, suggesting the involvement of mode I fibre bundle splitting during the fracture development.

Figure 8 Summary of specific work of fracture (SWF) for all ligament lengths

Table 4 G_{IIc} (in kJ/m^2) from ENF tests

Non-linear	5% offset	Maximum load
2.35	3.39	3.44

In addition to splitting fibre bundles on the fracture surface, possibility of fibre buckling is also suggested by draping fiber in the ligament region, as shown in Figure 10 which shows reduction of the interlaminar thickness towards the central part of the ligament section (between the white arrows). The draping fibre is prone to buckling, and is only observed clearly from specimens of $L=6$ mm.

The above microscopic observation is supported by test results, as shown by the experimental data (open diamonds) in Figure 11(a) for peak load and 11(b) for displacement at the peak load. As shown in the figure, the peak load is clearly deviated from the linear trend, but the corresponding displacement still follows the linear trend reasonably well.

5.3 FE Modeling

In view of the involvement of fibre buckling in specimens with $L=6$ mm, the FE modeling was conducted only for L up to 5 mm. Through try-and-error to match results from the experiments, it was found that low stiffness of the adhesive that bonds the FRP piece with the aluminum tabs has to be considered in order to match the displacement

measured at the peak load. The simulated peak load and the corresponding displacement are also shown in Figure 11 in solid squares. The figure clearly suggests that values from the simulation match reasonably well with the experimental results.

Figure 9 Fracture surfaces from Iosipescu tests: 5mm (left) and 6mm (right)

Figure 10 Fibers in the ligament area

(a)

(b)

Figure 11 Results from experiments and FE modeling: (a) peak load and (b) displacement at peak load

Table 5 presents the simulation results that include percentage of energy consumption in the FRP piece for elastic and plastic deformation and for the damage generation that leads to formation of fracture surface. It is clear that a significant portion of the energy is used for elastic deformation, and only a very small fraction of the total energy, around 6-7% for FRP and even smaller in terms of total energy consumed during the test, for generating damage in the interlaminar region which leads to the formation of delamination crack. This suggests that the 2nd term on the right-hand side of the original formulation for the EWF method, Eqn. (6), is not limited to plastic deformation energy. As long as the non-essential part of energy consumption is proportional L^2 , w_e value can still be determined using equation (6) through linear regression to $L=0$. This condition is being further investigated while this paper is prepared, and the results will be presented in the conference.

Table 5 Energy distribution in the FRP piece at the peak load of Iosipescu test

L (mm)	2	3	4	5
Elastic	74.2%	74.0%	73.4%	71.8%
Plastic	19.6%	19.7%	20.2%	21.4%
Damage	6.2%	6.3%	6.4%	6.7%

6 Conclusions

A regression analysis is successfully applied to Iosipescu test results of DEN specimens, to determine interlaminar fracture toughness in pure

shear mode. The fracture toughness value (w_e) is consistent with that from the popular ENF tests.

The study shows that the experimental results can be reasonably reproduced using finite element modeling. Based on results from the FE modeling, majority of the energy consumption during the test is for elastic deformation and the energy for fracture surface formation is only a very small portion of the total energy.

Further study will be conducted using FE modeling, to examine validity of the EWF formulation, equation (6), for the Iosipescu test, and appropriateness of linear regression for removing the non-essential part of energy consumption. Results from the FE modeling will be presented in the conference.

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